

VIRUS V/S SALIVARY GLAND: VIRAL ETIOLOGY IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF SALIVARY GLAND TUMORS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Salivary gland tumors, a diverse group of lesions that by its rarity as well as clinical, histological and morphological diversity pose a challenge to the pathologist. The role of oncogenic viruses in the pathogenesis of salivary gland has been studied and researched from as early as the 1950s. Even with the advent of newer diagnostic techniques, researches done to establish a relationship between salivary gland tumors and oncogenic viruses has reached a standstill because of the controversies in the results obtained from previous studies **Aim:** To critically analyse the literature available correlating oncogenic viruses in the development of salivary gland tumors in an attempt to establish the role of oncogenic viruses in salivary gland tumors. **Materials and Methods:** Articles published till 2018 December were chosen for the study. Articles were chosen for the study by the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the PRISMA checklist was followed for the selection of the articles for this study. **Results:** Total of 285 articles were obtained after searching databases like PUBMED, EMBASE, LILACS, COCHRANE, and after the screening, the collected articles following the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 24 articles were selected and analysed. **Conclusion:** After analysing all the selected articles, it was found that there could be a possible role of oncogenic viruses in the pathogenesis of salivary gland neoplasms. Among the viruses studied, HPV, EBV and CMV were the ones that have been shown to have an increased association in comparison with the other viruses in question. Further studies correlating these viruses are needed for further justification of the statement.

KEYWORDS Oncogenic Virus, Salivary gland tumors, HPV, Herpes virus, Polyomavirus, HIV

Introduction

Salivary gland tumors are a group of tumors which present with clinical, morphological and histological diversity posing a challenge to the pathologist in diagnosing these lesions. Though the majority of the salivary gland neoplasms that are reported are benign lesions, they represent 0.5% of all malignancies as well as 5% of the malignancies in the head and neck region. [1] Their rarity, as well as the diversity in their presentation, makes them

a fascinating area attracting much research in this area. These characters also make their diagnosis and management difficult. General dental practitioner lacks the knowledge required to manage and diagnose these lesions and often approach specialist centres for help.

Oncogenic viruses are viruses that can cause cancer; it refers to any DNA or RNA viruses who by its own or through its genome causes malignant transformation. The WHO National Cancer Research Agency in the year 2014 has estimated that 17.8% of cancer in humans are caused by viruses. [2] Viruses are implicated in the pathogenesis of tumors from as early as the 1990s. Plentiful viruses both DNA and RNA viruses are implicated in many tumors like HPV in squamous cell carcinoma, EBV in Burkitt's lymphoma and nasopharyngeal carcinoma, etc.[2] The relationship between viruses and pathogenesis of salivary gland has been in debate from the 90s but yet the results by

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different authors have contradicting views making a clear association grim. [3] Many oncogenic DNA viruses like EBV, HPV, SV40, polyoma virus etc are implicated to be associated with the development of various benign as well as malignant salivary gland tumors by many researchers in the past two decades, and this association is discarded by many other studies conducted. [4,5]

Most debated association between salivary gland tumor and viruses is the role of Epstein Barr Virus in Warthin's tumor, though many authors have proved their relationship through numerous studies there were some authors who disproved this relation in their study. Even amid all these confusions, numerous studies are still going on to establish their relation. A systematic review was done to correlate oncogenic viruses to the development of salivary gland tumors in an attempt to establish the role of oncogenic viruses in salivary gland tumors. A systematic review was chosen as it is the gold standard in evidence-based medicine for identification, evaluation as well as for summarising the association between the two variables.

Aim

There has been many controversies regarding the association of oncogenic viruses in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumors. The study aimed to critically analyse the literature available correlating oncogenic viruses to the development of salivary gland tumors in an attempt to establish a conclusion to their association.

Material and Methods

We have performed a systematic review by considering salivary gland tumors as the dependent variable and oncogenic viruses as the independent variable.

Search strategy

A systematic review involves critical analysis of multiple existing studies done in the field of interest. To answer our question of whether there is an association between oncogenic viruses and salivary gland, a systematic literature search using a combination of keywords was done. PUBMED, LILACS, EMBASE and COCHRANE were the search engines that were used for the collection of articles. Keywords used were salivary gland tumor, oncogenic virus, DNA virus, RNA virus in various combinations. Only invitro studies conducted in humans for the past ten years were included in the study. (Figure 1)

Inclusion criteria

Articles published until December 2018 were selected for the study. Only invitro studies in humans were included in the study. Articles with full text and published in the English language were selected.

Exclusion criteria

Articles published in languages other than English were excluded. Articles without full text were excluded. Articles which do not mention the correlation between oncogenic viruses in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumors were excluded. Articles that correlate tumors of another lineage with viruses were excluded. Case reports, Review articles and Letter to the editor were excluded. The article was written according to the PRISMA guidelines.

Figure1 Flow diagram representing systematic literature search on oncogenic virus in salivary gland tumorigenesis outcomes

Results

The keyword search strategy identified 285 suitable abstracts; 185 articles from PUBMED, 56 from EMBASE, ten from LILAC and 1 article from the Cochrane database, from these 38 articles were excluded after reviewing the title and abstract after screening as they did not meet the eligibility criteria. Full-text articles were obtained for 83 articles. Sixty-four articles were excluded from the study for various reasons, case reports, reviews and letter to the editor were excluded, and any article published in languages other than English. Finally, after considering all the inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of 19 articles were included in the study. Figure 1 shows a PRISMA diagram for this review. The selected studies were screened, and the specific study characteristics were recorded in Table 1.

Discussion

In this study, we analysed 19 articles obtained through screening based on PRISMA guidelines to establish an association between oncogenic viruses and salivary gland tumors.

Oncogenic viruses are one of the most debated agents, causing tumors in a different part of the body. The association of viruses in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumor has been a topic of discussion and a field of interest in various researches since the 1950s. Numerous studies have been conducted in both animal as well as humans since then, but there has been much contradiction in the results obtained. This muddle in reaching an absolute answer hampers further understanding of this concept as well as the opportunity of developing newer targeted therapies as well as preventive agents to bring this disease down to the ground. [24]

It is known that DNA viruses cause tumors in humans whereas RNA viruses cause tumors in animals except for HHV-8 which causes Kaposi sarcoma in humans and HCV which causes hepatocellular carcinoma in humans. [25]

In the studies selected for the systemic review, the viruses commonly encountered were HPV, EBV, CMV and POLYOMA virus with few articles mentioning leukaemia virus and HHV-8.

Human PapillomaVirus

They are a group of DNA viruses belonging to the Papillomaviridae family. It is a non-enveloped DNA virus. They are larger

Table 1 Overview of selected studies.

Name of author and year of study	Salivary gland tumor included in the study	Virus implicated in pathogenesis	Methods used	Inference
Saemundensen et al, 1985 [6]	Salivary gland carcinomas	EBV	EBV DNA antibody levels were titred.	Positive correlation between salivary gland carcinomas and EBV.
Traub et al, 1991 [7]	Undifferentiated carcinoma	EBV	Analysis of Epstein-Barr virus transcription in situ in parotid carcinoma specimens revealed that the EBER RNAs, latent membrane protein mRNA, and the BamHI-A rightward reading frame, BARF0, are expressed in the malignant epithelial cells.	There is a strong association between EBV and undifferentiated carcinoma.
Leung et al, 1995[6]	Lymphoepithelial carcinoma	EBV	In situ hybridisation was used to localise EBER RNA, immunohistochemical methods to detect expression of latent membrane protein 1 (LMP-1) in EBV positive tumours, and Southern blot analysis to examine the clonality of EBV in the two cases where frozen tissue was available.	Consistent association between EBV and lymphoepithelial carcinoma.
Martinelli et al, 2002[7]	Pleomorphic adenoma	Simian Virus 40	DNA extraction followed by RT-PCR and then filter hybridisation was done. DNA sequencing of the samples were done and then immunohistochemical study using mouse anti-SV40 Tag monoclonal antibody to confirm presence of SV40 was performed.	SV-40 Tag is a transforming protein which behaves like an activated oncogene. SV-40 may act like a cofactor in the development of salivary gland tumor.
Jen et al, 2003 [10]	Lymphoepithelial carcinomas	EBV	IHC using mouse monoclonal antibody against EBV LMP1 and then in-situ hybridisation was done to confirm presence of EBV. DNA extraction and PCR followed by DNA sequencing were done.	Mutation in LM[-1 in EBV promotes cell proliferation and may play a role in development of lyphoepithelial carcinoma.
Michael Melnick et al, 2012[8]	Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	Cytomegalovirus	Immunohistochemistry for active human CMV proteins IE1- 72and pp65	The first study to have established a correlation between CMV and salivary gland carcinoma.

Weijia Liu et al, 2012[9]	Benign and malignant salivary gland tumors	HIV (CXCL12 G801A polymorphism)	PCR followed by DNA sequencing for detection of CXCL12 G801A polymorphism	The CXCL12 G801A polymorphism is present in benign salivary gland neoplasm and absent in malignant neoplasm suggesting a possible association in these lesions,
Markus Brunner, 2012[10]	Minor salivary gland mucoepidermoid carcinoma	HPV 16 and 18	In-situ hybridisation for detection of HPV	The study was the first of its kind to establish a relationship between high risk HPV 16 and 18 and minor salivary gland mucoepidermoid carcinoma.
Layla Hafed et al, 2012[4]	Warthin's tumor, Pleomorphic adenoma, Myoepithelioma Lymphoma	HPV 16 and 18	Tissue hybridisation using labelled DNA probes	Established that there is a relation between histogenesis of salivary gland neoplasms and HPV viruses.
Géraldine Descamps et al, 2012[11]	Pleomorphic adenomas, Acini cell carcinoma, Carcinoma ex-pleomorphic adenoma	High and low risk HPV	PCR was done following DNA extraction and Immunohistochemistry for detection of p16.	There is o prominent role of HPV in the tumorigenesis of salivary gland tumors.
Tatyana Isayeva et al, 2013[12]	Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	HPV16&18	RNA extraction was initially done and then PCR was performed for amplification of the sample and then immunofluorescence was done to look for HPV16/18 E6.	HR-HPV oncoproteins promote MEC as a later event in multistep carcinogenesis.
Alena Skálová et al, 2013[5]	Pleomorphic adenoma, Warthin's tumor, Myoepithelioma, Oncocytoma, Cystadenoma, Basal cell adenoma, PLGA, Cribriform adenocarcinoma	HPV 16&18	In p16 positive samples DNA amplification was done using PCR for specific primers for HPV 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 45. Amplicons were then analysed using ethidium bromide.	There is no role of HPV 16&18 in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumors.
Wei-Qiang Teng et al, 2013[13]	Pleomorphic adenoma, Adenoma of salivary gland, Gland lymphoma, Myoepithelioma, Adenocarcinoma, Adenoid cystic carcinoma, Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	37 types of HPV	Flow through amplification was done in samples obtained by PCR amplification following DNA extraction	HPV is associated with salivary gland tumors especially 16,18&52.

Fisher et al, 2014[14]	Small cell carcinoma of parotid	Merkel cell polyoma virus	Immunohistochemistry for neuroendocrine markers (chromogranin A, CD56, CD57, neuron-specific enolase [NSE], thyroid transcription factor 1 [TTF-1]), epithelial markers (CK20, CK7, CAM 5.2), and MCPyV large T antigen (LTag).	Suggested a possible relationship between MCPyV and small cell carcinoma of parotid.
Shanehsazzadeh et al, 2014[15]	Pleomorphic adenoma, Monomorphic adenoma, Mucoepidermoid carcinoma, Adenoid cystic carcinoma	HHV6&7	DNA extraction was done and the obtained samples were then used for RT-PCR for primers specific to HHV-6&7.	There is no relation between salivary gland tumor and HHV 6&7.
Bishop et al, 2014[16]	Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	High risk HPV	MAML-2 immunofluorescence and HPV RNA in-situ hybridisation were done.	There is no role of HPV in development of MEC.
Feng Lin et al, 2014[17]	Pleomorphic adenoma, Warthin's tumor	HPV and EBV	Direct sequencing for HPV protein followed by RT-PCR for confirmation of presence of HPV and RT-PCR for detection of EBV.	Established role if these viruses in development of salivary gland tumors.
Huhns et al, 2015[18]	Benign and Malignant salivary gland neoplasms	HPV, EBV, HHV-8	Tissue microarrays are constructed for conducting immunohistochemistry using primary antibodies against Cytokeratin AE1/AE3, EBV-latent membrane protein-1 (LMP-1), HHV-8 and p16.	HPV is associated with salivary gland tumors whereas EBV & HHV-8 has no association in the development of these tumors.
Miah et al, 2015[19]	Pleomorphic adenoma, Warthin's tumor, Malignant salivary gland tumors, Metastatic salivary gland tumors	HPV	Tissue microarrays are constructed for conducting immunohistochemistry using p16 and in-situ hybridisation using probes specific for HPV.	There was no significant relation between salivary gland tumors and HPV.
Qian et al, 2016[20]	Adenoid cystic carcinoma	HPV	DNA extraction and HPV genotyping following by PCR amplification was done. Immunohistochemistry using mouse anti-p16 antibody or mouse anti-human EGFR monoclonal antibody was then done.	There is association between ACC and HPV. P16 expressed by HPV can be a reliable marker in detection of ACC.

Radunovic et al, 2016[21]	Malignant salivary gland tumors	CMV	Immunohistochemistry to detect and determine intensity of IL-6 and CMV antigen in tumor tissue.	External environmental factors alter the salivary gland cells making them more susceptible for CMV infection. CMV increases production of IL-6 which inhibits apoptosis and promoted tumor development.
Chen et al, 2017[3]	Pleomorphic adenoma, Warthin's tumor, Mucoepidermoid carcinoma, Primary squamous cell carcinoma	22 alpha HPV strains, 25 beta HPV strains, 5 Herpes virus, 10 Polyoma virus		Compared large group of viruses against salivary gland tumors. Beta HPV, polyoma viruses, EBV, CMV were found in various salivary gland tumor specimens analysed. EBV were associated more with Warthin's tumor and CMV with malignant tumor.
Ramqvist et al, 2018[22]	Malignant salivary gland tumors	10 Polyoma virus	DNA extraction followed by multiplex PCR and bead-based Luminex technology were performed.	Polyoma viruses are not important etiological factors in the development of salivary gland tumors.
Haegglblom et al, 2018[23]	Malignant salivary gland tumors	27 HPV	DNA extraction followed by multiplex PCR was done. Presence of HPV was confirmed by IHC using p16.	There is no causal relationship between HPV and malignant salivary gland tumor.

than polyomaviruses with a larger genome of size eight kbp. They induce hyperplasia of epithelial cell in the infected body. More than 7- types of HPV types have been identified. They exhibit significant tissue as well as cell specificity and infect only the surface epithelium of the skin as well as mucosal surfaces. [26] The list of diseases caused by various HPV is listed in Table 2.

Among the 19 articles reviewed, 14 articles have correlated HPV with salivary gland neoplasm either alone or in combination with other viruses. In these 14 articles, ten articles have correlated various strains of HPV with various benign and malignant salivary gland tumors. Most of the researches have been done with HPV-16&18 (high-risk HPV). In this, nine articles have established a positive association between HPV and salivary gland tumor, whereas five articles have proposed that there no relation between these two.

Herpes virus

Herpesvirus is a family of viruses that contain several of the essential human pathogens and comprise of over 100 species of DNA viruses are a part of this family. They express a wide host cell range and ability to establish latent infections, produce life-long persistent infection and also undergo periodic reactivation. Herpes simplex viruses were one of the first herpes viruses to

be recognised. [27] It is of two types Type 1 HSV which causes infections above the waist line especially localised to around the mouth. Type 2 HSV on the other hand, causes genital, sexually transmitted infections. (28)Cytomegalovirus is a group of ubiquitous herpesviruses of humans and animals which produces swollen cells containing large intranuclear inclusion bodies and are the largest of all herpes viruses. Epstein-Barr Virus is a type of virus first described by Burkitt in Burkitt's lymphoma as a virus transmitted by mosquito. It is a group of viruses that has specificity for infecting B-lymphocytes. The diseases caused by these viruses are listed in Table 2.

There were six studies conducted with various herpes viruses, like CMV, EBV, HHV-8. One study correlated all the three viruses along with HPV and POLYOMA virus and suggested a possible role of EBV in the pathogenesis of Warthin's tumor and that CMV was more commonly associated with malignant salivary gland tumors and may play a role in their pathogenesis. Three studies attempted to establish a relation between CMV and salivary gland tumor; three studies correlated CMV with mucoepidermoid carcinoma. The last one compared with various malignant salivary gland tumors. All the three studies suggested a possible role of the virus in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumors.

In the seven studies conducted with EBV, six studies suggested a possible role of EBV in salivary gland neoplasm, but

Table 2 List of diseases caused by HPV, herpes and polyoma viruses.

VIRUS	DISEASES CAUSED BY THE VIRUS
Human papilloma virus	Warts, Epidermodysplasia verruciformis, Recurrent respiratory papillomatosis, Oral papillomas, Condyloma accuminatum, Florid epithelial hyperplasia.[25,28] Carcinomas of oral cavity (SCC), cervix (Cervical intra-epithelial neoplasia), anogenital region etc. [30,31]
Herpes simplex virus	Herpetic gingivostomatitis, Herpetic whitlow, Herpesfebrilis, Herpes gladiatorium, Eczema herpeticum, genital herpes, Herpes encephalitis, Herpes meningitis [25,28,32]
Cytomegalovirus	Infectious mononucleosis like symptoms, flu-like symptoms, retinitis.[25,28]
Ebstein-Barr virus	Infectious mononucleosis, Burkitt's lymphoma, Nasopharyngeal carcinoma, Oral hairy leukoplakia[25,28,33]
BK virus	Polyoma associated nephropathy, Hemorrhagic cystitis.[29]
JC virus	Progressive multifocal leukoencephalopathy.[29]
Simian virus 40	Brain tumor, Bone tumor, Mesotheliomas, Hodgkin's lymphoma. [29]

one study proposed that there is no relationship between the two. It is one of the first viruses to be detected in salivary gland neoplasms and has been since then implicated to be an etiological agent in the pathogenesis of Warthin's tumor as well as lymphoepithelial carcinoma.

Two studies have attempted to assess the role of HHV-8, and one study has been done with HSV and has proposed that these viruses have no role in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumors.

Polyomavirus

Polyomaviruses are a group of small viruses with the circular genome of double-stranded DNA within the non-enveloped capsid. Cellular histones inside the viral genome will condense the viral DNA inside the viral particle. They are species specific like HPV. Medically relevant members of this family of viruses are BK virus, JC virus, SV-40 and mouse polyomavirus. (28) They are asymptomatic in normal individuals but cause tumors or infections in immunocompromised individuals. BK virus has been associated with nephropathy in renal transplant patients, and JC virus is associated with progressive multifocal leukoencephalopathy. Merkel cell virus causes Merkel cell carcinoma. The most significant member of this viral family is SV-40, which causes tumors of the brain, bone, mesotheliomas and Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas. (29). The diseases caused by these viruses are listed in Table 2.

Four studies have been conducted with polyomaviruses and the salivary gland neoplasms. In that one study by Fischer et al., was done on Merkel cell polyomavirus and small cell carcinoma, and they have established a possible association between both. In the other two studies, ten polyomaviruses were analysed, Simian virus 40 has been implicated to have a

more likely Association in the causation of salivary gland tumors in comparison with others.

Human Immunodeficiency Virus

HIV is a group of RNA viruses derived from primate lentiviruses, belonging to the family of HTLV and are etiologic of one of the most feared diseases known to man Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome or AIDS. There are two types of HIV: HIV1 and HIV 2. In a study conducted by Liu et al., they looked for CXCL12 G801A polymorphism (seen in HIV infection) in both benign and malignant salivary gland tumor and found a positive association with benign salivary gland tumor.

Conclusion

There have been numerous studies conducted in the role of oncogenic viruses in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumors. Still, there were lots of controversies regarding this. In the systematic review, we conducted, we were able to conclude that there is a possible correlation of these viruses, especially, HPV, EBV and CMV in the pathogenesis of salivary gland tumors. Further studies with large samples are required correlating these viruses with various salivary gland neoplasms to justify this statement. Once established with proper supportive evidence, this aspect may change the therapeutic as well as preventive measures currently in place to deal with these neoplasms.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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References

1. Jagdish AK, Janarthanam J, Parthasarathy S, Santosham K. Histogenetic and Morphogenetic Concepts of Salivary Gland Neoplasms. 2014;3(11):575–81.
2. Weiss RA. Oncogenic viruses and cancer transmission. *Cancer Assoc Viruses*. 2012;30(2):101–18.
3. Chen AA, Gheit T, Stellin M, Lupato V, Spinato G, Fuson R, et al. Oncogenic DNA viruses found in salivary gland tumors. *Oral Oncol* [Internet]. 2017;75(October):106–10. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oraloncology.2017.11.005>
4. Hafed L, Farag H, Shaker O, El-rouby D. Is human papilloma virus associated with salivary gland neoplasms? An in situ-hybridization study. *Arch Oral Biol* [Internet]. 2012;57(9):1194–9. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.archoralbio.2012.03.009>
5. Skálová A, Ka J, Andrlé P, Hostiáka L, Vanůáek T. Human papillomaviruses are not involved in the etiopathogenesis of salivary gland tumors. 2013;(5):72–5.
6. SY Leung, L P Chung, ST YUen, C M Ho, M P Wong SYC. Lymphoepithelial carcinoma of the salivary gland: in situ detection of Epstein-Barr virus. 1995;48(11):1–5.
7. Martinelli M, Martini F, Rinaldi E, Caramanico L, Magri E, Grandi E, et al. Simian virus 40 sequences and expression of the viral large T antigen oncoprotein in human pleomorphic adenomas of parotid glands. *Am J Pathol* [Internet]. 2002;161(4):1127–33. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9440\(10\)64389-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9440(10)64389-1)
8. Melnick M, Sedghizadeh PP, Allen CM, Jaskoll T. Human cytomegalovirus and mucoepidermoid carcinoma of salivary glands: Cell-specific localization of active viral and oncogenic signaling proteins is confirmatory of a causal relationship. *Exp Mol Pathol* [Internet]. 2012;92(1):118–25. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.yexmp.2011.10.011>
9. Liu W, Zhu E, Wang R. CXCL12 G801A polymorphism is associated with an increased risk of benign salivary gland tumors in the Chinese population. 2012;677–81.
10. Brunner M, Koperek O, Schoppper C, Thurnher D. HEAD AND NECK HPV infection and p16 expression in carcinomas of the minor salivary glands. 2012;2265–9.
11. Descamps G, Duray A, Rodriguez A, Chantrain G, Depuydt CE, Delvenne P, et al. Detection and quantification of human papillomavirus in benign and malignant parotid lesions. *Anticancer Res*. 2012;32(9):3929–32.
12. Isayeva T, Said-al-naief N, Ren Z, Li R, Gnepp D, Brandwein-gensler M. Salivary Mucoepidermoid Carcinoma: Demonstration of Transcriptionally Active Human. 2013;7(2):135–48.
13. Wei-Qiang Teng, Xiao-Ping Chen, Xiao-Cheng Xue, Yi Zhang, Xue-Jun Tan, Guangbin Sun, Yan Wang LW. Distribution of 37 human papillomavirus types in parotid gland tumor tissues. *Oncol Lett* [Internet]. 2013;1(5):797–800. Available from: <https://www.spandidos-publications.com/ol/1/5/797>
14. Fisher CA, Harms PW, Mchugh JB, Edwards PC, Siddiqui J, Palanisamy N, et al. Small cell carcinoma in the parotid harboring Merkel cell polyomavirus. *Oral Surgery, Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol* [Internet]. 2014;118(6):703–12. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oooo.2014.09.012>
15. Shanehsazzadeh M, Rad JS-, Pourazar A, Behbahani M. Epidemiology of Herpes Human Virus 6 and 7 Infections in Salivary Gland Neoplasms in Isfahan, 2014;68(4):276–8.
16. Bishop JA, Yonescu R, Batista D, Yemelyanova A, Ha PK, Westra WH. Mucoepidermoid Carcinoma Does Not Harbor Transcriptionally Active High Risk Human Papillomavirus Even in the Absence of the MAML2 Translocation. 2014;8(3):298–302.
17. Lin FC, Chen PL, Tsao TY, Li CR, Jeng KC, Tsai SC. Prevalence of human papillomavirus and Epstein-Barr virus in salivary gland diseases. *J Int Med Res*. 2014;42(5):1093–101.
18. Hühns M, Simm G, Erbersdobler A, Zimpfer A. HPV Infection , but Not EBV or HHV-8 Infection , Is Associated with Salivary Gland Tumours. 2015;
19. Miah MS, Majumdar S, White S, Robinson M, Kernohan N. Human papillomavirus and salivary gland neoplasia: a p16 INK4 immunohistochemical and in situ hybridisation study. 2015;(January):1000–3.
20. Xu Qian, Andreas M. Kaufmann, Chao Chen, Georgios Tzamalidis, Veit M. Hofmann, Ulrich Keilholz, Michael Hummel AEA. Prevalence and associated survival of high-risk HPV-related adenoid cystic carcinoma of the salivary glands. *Int J Oncol*. 2016;1–16.
21. Milena Radunovic, Nada Tomanovic, Ivana Novakovic IB. Virus induces Interleukin-6 mediated inflammatory response in salivary gland cancer F. *J Balk union Oncol*. 2016;6(21):1–23.
22. Ramqvist T, Ursu RG, Haeggbloom L, Mirzaie L. Human Polyomaviruses Are Not Frequently Present in Cancer of the Salivary Glands. 2018;2874:2871–4.
23. Haeggbloom L, Ursu RG, Mirzaie L, Attoff T, Gahm C, Nordenvall LH. No evidence for human papillomavirus having a causal role in salivary gland tumors. *J dianstic Pathol*. 2018;1–12.
24. Rowe BWP, Hartley JW, Estes JD, Huebner RJ. STUDIES OF MOUSE POLYOMA VIRUS INFECTION VIRUS (From the United States Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, Public Health Service, National Institutes of Health, National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, Laboratory of Infectio. 1959;379–91.
25. F.H.Kayser. *Medical Microbiology*. Vol. 71. 2005. 434-438 p.

26. Cell T, Marrow B. KRAUSE ' S ESSENTIAL HUMAN HISTOLOGY FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS Third Edition William J . Krause, Ph. D. Professor of Anatomy Department of Pathology and Anatomical Sciences University of Missouri School of Medicine Columbia, Missouri Table of Contents. :1–315.
27. Whitley RJ. Chapter 68, Herpesviruses. Med Microbiol [Internet]. 1996;(1):1–15. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK8157>
28. Kumar S. Textbook of microbiology. 2012.
29. De Caprio Garcea. Polyomaviridae. 2017;(2016):1–16.
30. Handisurya A, Schellenbacher C, Kirnbauer R. Diseases caused by human papillomaviruses (HPV). J Ger Soc Dermatol. 2009;2009(Band 7):60–70.
31. Doorbar J, Egawa N, Griffin H, Kranjec C, Murakami I. Human papillomavirus molecular biology and disease association. Rev Med Virol. 2015;25(S1):2–23.
32. Mustafa M, Illzam E, Muniandy R, Sharifah A, Nang M, Ramesh B. Herpes simplex virus infections, Pathophysiology and Management. IOSR J Dent Med Sci [Internet]. 2016;15(07):85–91. Available from: <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jdms/papers/Vol15-Issue7/Version-3/Q150738591.pdf>
33. Grinde B. Herpesviruses: latency and reactivation – viral strategies and host response. J Oral Microbiol [Internet]. 2013;5(1):22766. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.3402/jom.v5i0.22766>